

D3.1

Quality label definition

skillbill

SKILL TO BOOST INNOVATION & PROFESSIONAL
FULFILLMENT IN A SUSTAINABLE ECONOMY

AzeroCO2

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ABBREVIATIONS

AB	Advisory Board
CA	Consortium Agreement
EC	European Commission
RES	Renewable energy sources
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This deliverable describes the Quality Label set up for the Horizon Europe SKILLBILL project, laying out the strategy that will guide the consortium on its use during the project's lifecycle.

The Quality Label will be applied on the information material uploaded in the Green Portal; its purpose is both: to guarantee the reliability and to give immediate visual recognition of the content, using several evaluation categories.

This report is structured as follows:

Chapter 1: the **SKILLBILL Green Portal** description and its goals.

Chapter 2: the **Quality Label** description and its goals, with application rules

Chapter 3: Overview of the Green Portal

The verification of the effective use of the Green Portal and the appreciation of its contents will be performed during the project lifetime, using online feedbacks forms; the results will be elaborated in the final version of Deliverable D6.4 at Month 36.

1. Green Portal

1.1 Description

Despite the presence of several information resources online, finding a reliable, up-to-date, and complete portal on renewable energy technologies is complicated.

The Green Portal is conceived to offer a comprehensive educational recipient on renewable energy technologies: a platform to help people understand the renewable energy technologies and GHG meaning and impact on climate change.

The technologies are, at least, solar photovoltaic and thermal, wind, hydro, geothermal, biofuels (biomethane, bioethanol and biodiesel), gasification, digestion, biomass combustion, hydrogen and fuel cells; the portal will also point out how adopting the proper technologies in everyday life will contribute to efficient mitigation of climate change.

The platform will host the link to the original video or document, giving a short abstract or explanation of the content. This is conceived to avoid problems on intellectual properties or copyrights.

The portal will host mainly already available materials but also new ones, developed during the project lifetime by the other WPs: the intent of the portal is not to create new material but to better organise the good ones available on the internet while checking the consistency of the contents.

1.2 Sections

The green portal has different sections:

- Green e-board discussion/forum: serves as an open environment for exchanging information, asking questions on RES, exchanging experiences, and receiving information, good practices and suggestions by experts. This activity will take place on a social media platform of the project (such as Facebook) where users can ask for a specific question or express their agreements /disagreements.
- Green woman: a dedicated section of material on Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics (STEM) done by women or talking about the relationship between women and STEM. This section is conceived to value female talent in technology, innovation and scientific research, promoting projects and actions aimed at combating stereotypes and gender discrimination, contributing to the orientation of young people to the jobs of the future and towards sustainable business models, and finally encouraging women to exploit their full potential in STEM¹. The need to have a greater participation of women in STEM/ technical fields is described in several studies, that have shown that women researchers, designers, installers and even final users face both covert and overt gender discrimination². The scholarly community usually offers them inadequate professional support, important for career advancement. Beyond higher education, UNESCO³ observed that globally men still wield more power across diverse societies and women do not benefit from their education to the same

¹ www.womentech.eu

² www.eige.europa.eu

³ <http://uis.unesco.org/en/topic/women-science>

extent. Women often require more effort to get the same jobs, encounter discrimination and disparities of power, having difficulty to achieve their full potential. This section wants to steer the involvement of youngsters thanks to the sense of participation in a community and the presence of strong positive female role models; social environmental influencers will inspire them to follow the path.

- **Green schools:** this section is dedicated to students, starting from younger to more advanced learners. Instructional materials are needed to convey ideas to the students to enhance their understanding; the materials are the basic components in teaching at all levels of education, especially higher education. The materials and resources provide opportunities for students to broaden and deepen their knowledge by providing a variety of appropriate experiences and by helping students acquire knowledge. Material can include: educational videos, tutorials for realisation of demonstrators, explanation of processes and technologies, role-play game; quizzes and educational cards, interactive games¹, training videos (also coming from the Master developed in WP4), experiential exhibits in existing public spaces (e.g. science and tech museums); informative factsheets, 60 second science videos, etc.
- **Good practice database:** this section is dedicated to collect young careers testimonials and RES job profiles factsheets and requests; the database provides a searchable repository of good practices and lessons learned on RES, on the best way to use the proper technology on everyday life, with dissemination of experience, transfer of practices / development of new approaches with activities based on transfer of practice and development of implementation plans.
- **Knowledge hub:** access to knowledge on specific policy areas (e.g., policy briefs, webinars, reports, other platforms); in this section it will be possible to search for all the material uploaded in the portal using specific filters.

Figure 1: Green Portal site map

¹ <https://www.epa.gov/students/games-quizzes-and-videos-about-environment>

The overview of the portal is given in paragraph 3.

1.3 Filters

The portal is structured with filters that will help the user to find the material available.

The filters are:

- **Macrocategory/web section**
 - Green woman
 - Green schools
 - Good practice database
 - Knowledge hub

- **RES category (Renewable sources of energy)^{1, 2}**
 - Solar power
 - Biomass
 - Biofuel
 - Wind power
 - Geothermal energy
 - Hydrogen
 - Hydroelectric power
 - Ocean energy

- **RES and efficiency technology [RES category]**
 - PV [Solar power]
 - Solar thermal [Solar power]
 - Biomass combustion, gasification systems, pyrolysis [Biomass]
 - Biogas/biomethane/bio-diesel/bio-ethanol/others [Biomass]; [Biofuel]
 - Wind turbine [Wind power]
 - Geothermal high/low enthalpy [Geothermal energy]
 - Hydrogen [Hydrogen]
 - Fuel cells and storage [Hydrogen]
 - Hydroelectric turbines and plants [Hydroelectric power]
 - Tidal Stream/Wave Energy/OTEC/SWAC/Salinity Gradient [Ocean energy]³
 - Heat pumps
 - Other (e.g. energy efficiency/GHG/ climate change/ Zero Energy Buildings....)

- **Type of material**
 - Video
 - Manual/guide (technical)

¹ <https://www.un.org/en/climatechange/what-is-renewable-energy>

² <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/70/renewable-energy>

³ <https://www.oceanenergy-europe.eu/>

- Policy/ regulatory
 - Game
 - Scientific article
 - Informative educational article/news/interview
 - Projects
 - Other
- **Language**

Other additional info will be available in the description of the material, such as:

- Year of publication

Filters shall be added or replaced in the first months of the portal, in case the ones initially chosen are not functional enough. Regarding the filter “**RES category**” we have followed the classification of the European Union on renewables sources adding few other choices. Regarding the “**RES technology**” several different technologies have been clustered in order to make the choice easier for all the types of users.

The QUALITY LABEL will be used as an additional filter as well and will be fully described in the following chapter 2.

It is feasible that several materials will have more than one filter, so those will be findable under different categories.

1.3.1 *How to use the filters*

The users can select one or more filters to narrow down and customise the search results, according to the material they are interested in.

The user can find exactly what he/she wants by selecting the Macrocategory /Web section; RES category; Language; Quality Label.

1.4 Interactions between users

The portal will be connected with the website and the socials of the project. In this way users can comment on the material and ask for additional info and all people, even external to the project, can contribute to the discussion in an open and constructive way.

A facilitator and automatic tools will moderate interventions if not in line with the topics or if violent, with prejudice and not following the ethics, screening for inappropriate or harmful posts within the platform¹.

¹ <https://www.coe.int/en/web/gender-matters/advice-on-facilitation-of-activities>

In socials, people will be able to express their agreement on the material also in a simple act, such as leaving a “like”.

The portal will also allow people to subscribe for further information, to receive the newsletter as well as a notification when new material (or material of interest) is being uploaded.

1.4.1 *Competition for schools*

A social game will be launched for students: a sort of competition between schools or classes on topics related to climate change and RES; the winner could be chosen between the ones who have received a higher score of “like” in the socials. A prize will be decided along with the rules for the participation; all will be published within an adequate time frame.

Below is reported a non-exhaustive list of possible contents, in group or for singular student, that will be further discussed and fully explained within the consortium and the Scientific Advisory:

- A video performing an experiment on RES
- Picture of RES
- A series of short interviews on a specific topic (related to RES) between students or outside the schools.
- A short composition on RES: no more than 3 pages on a specific topic: sustainability; specific RES, their application... like a scientific paper and/or like a ppt presentation and/or like a short pitch
- A paper with suggestion on the way to increase the sustainability on the school or the whole surrounding area
- Making a 3d plastic of a RES technique

An initial screening of the material will be performed by the schools that agreed to participate.

Having different schools in different countries: we can ask to work together on one topic, so students can exchange point of views, noticing (probably) the different approach in different countries.

The possible process:

1. The school decides with SKILLBILL the content/ material to create; topic, format
2. The school asks the students to create the material (to be discussed quantity and timeframe)
3. The tutor revises them and send to SKILLBILL the ones more valuable
4. SKILLBILL team revise the material to apply the green label and to publish it on the portal and /or the socials

1.5 Statistics

The portal will use the services of Google Analytics as a web analytics service that provides statistics and basic analytical tools for search engine optimization (SEO). The service is part of the Google Marketing Platform and is available for free to anyone with a Google account¹.

Google Analytics is used to track website performance and collect visitor insights. It can help to determine top sources of user traffic, track goal completions, discover patterns and trends, obtain other visitor information such as demographics, behaviour analytics, which can be used to improve the material, drive website traffic and better retain visitors.

The metrics we are going to track are:

- Number of visitors
- Time of permanence of the session
- User appreciation
- User interactions
- User convenience (country)

How does Google Analytics work?²

Google Analytics acquires user data from each website visitor through the use of page tags. A JavaScript page tag is inserted into the code of each page. This tag runs in the web browser of each visitor, collecting data and sending it to one of Google's data collection servers. Google Analytics can then generate customizable reports to track and visualize data such as the number of users, bounce rates, average session durations, sessions by channel, page views, goal completions and more. The page tag functions as a web bug or web beacon, to gather visitor information. However, because it relies on cookies, the system can't collect data for users who have disabled them. Google Analytics includes features that can help users identify trends and patterns in how visitors engage with their websites.

Features enable data collection, analysis, monitoring, visualization, reporting and integration with other applications. These features include:

- *data visualization and monitoring tools, including dashboards, scorecards and motion charts that display changes in data over time;*
- *data filtering, manipulation and funnel analysis;*
- *data collection application program interfaces (APIs);*
- *predictive analytics, intelligence and anomaly detection;*
- *segmentation for analysis of subsets, such as conversions;*
- *custom reports for advertising, acquisition, audience behaviour and conversion;*
- *email-based sharing and communication;*

Within the Google Analytics dashboard, users can save profiles for multiple websites and either see details for default categories or select custom metrics to display for each site. Available categories for tracking include content overview, keywords, referring sites, visitors overview, map overlay and traffic sources overview. The dashboard can be viewed on the Google Analytics site and is available through a widget or a plugin for embedding into other sites. Customized Google Analytics dashboards are also available from independent vendors.

Important metrics.

¹ <https://www.techtarget.com/searchbusinessanalytics/definition/Google-Analytics>

² <https://www.techtarget.com/searchbusinessanalytics/definition/Google-Analytics>

A metric is a standard of quantitative measurement. Google Analytics enables users to track up to 200 different metrics to measure how their websites are performing. While some metrics may be more valuable to certain businesses than others, these are some of the most popular metrics:

- **Users.** A user is a unique or new visitor to the website.
- **Bounce rate.** The percentage of visitors who viewed only a single page. These visitors only triggered a single request to the Google Analytics server.
- **Sessions.** The group of visitor interactions that happen in a 30-minute window of activity.
- **Average session duration.** How long on average each visitor stays on the site.
- **Percentage of new sessions.** The percentage of website visits that are first-time visits.
- **Pages per session.** The average number of page views per each session.
- **Goal completions.** The number of times visitors complete a specified, desirable action. This is also known as a conversion.
- **Page views.** Total number of pages viewed.

Metrics vs. dimensions

Google Analytics reports consist of dimensions and metrics. Understanding the difference between them is critical for proper interpretation of reports.

Dimensions. These are qualitative attributes or labels used to describe and organize data. For example, if the average session length is being measured across several different regions, the dimensions would be "Region." "Average session length," which is a quantitative measurement, is an example of a metric.

Dimensions can be customized in Google Analytics. Examples of common dimensions include:

- language;
- browser type;
- city and country;
- models of devices; and
- user age group.

Metrics. These are quantitative measurements of a single type of data. Examples of metrics include average session lengths, page views, pages per session and average time on site. Metrics are used to compare measurements across different dimensions.

User acquisition data vs. user behaviour data

Google Analytics can provide businesses with multiple types of data for marketing purposes.

- **User acquisition data** provides insight into how customers are arriving at the website. Customers may come from a variety of channels, such as paid search engine results, unpaid search engine results, social media links or simply typing in the URL. Understanding user acquisition data is critical for maximizing website traffic.
- **User behaviour data** shows what customers are doing on the website, and how they are engaging with the site. This includes how long they spend on each page, how many pages they visit, and if they engage with videos and graphics. This data can be used to create web layouts that better connect visitors with the content they are looking for, leading to a more effective user experience. User experiences optimized according to user behaviour data are more likely to create sales and conversions.

Benefits and limitations

Google Analytics has distinct benefits and limitations. Pros generally relate to the platform being powerful, free and user-friendly.

Google Analytics historically has some shortcomings that may affect its data accuracy.

1.6 Targeted audience and key messages

The green portal will provide comprehensive and effective information on RES technologies to a large audience; communication experts will ensure that communication reaches its goals, using simple, inclusive and adequate language, valorising the differences and specificities of each target group, taking charge of their specific needs.

Each material uploaded in the portal will be shortly described with adequate and clear information, using simple language, terminology and definitions.

Table 1: Key messages

Targeted audience	Dedicated section	Key messages
Women	Green women	Materials should not propagate gender stereotypes and should portray women in EMPOWERING roles wherever possible
Young people; Student	Green school	Material should generate CURIOSITY towards science, that should be easy to understand; educational, reliable and fun
Citizen	Good practice database Green board Knowledge hub	Material should generate TRUST towards science, it should be easy to understand, reliable, replicable, stimulating
Workers	Good practice database Green board Knowledge hub	Material should be RELEVANT, USEFUL and SIMPLE to enrich (UPSKILL/RESKILL) the knowhow
Scientist	Knowledge hub	Material should be RELEVANT to enrich (UPSKILL/RESKILL) the knowhow

2. Quality Label

2.1 Scope

The scope of the quality label is to immediately vehicle some basic information on the material uploaded on the Green Portal and to guarantee the scientific reliability of the contents.

The quality label is a pictogram that contains the first indicators in a visual fashion, so that they can be immediately recognised.

The Quality Label is conceived to:

- Provide immediate basic information to help people to navigate through the material easily and in the way they need it.
- Provide Identification, differentiating the material from each other, since the portal gives place to several options.
- Give a description: Quality Label provides descriptive information, such as the level and the type of user the material is indicated for.
- Make material comparison: Quality Label contains pictograms and colours for different levels and users, so it's going to be easy to make a basic comparison between materials.
- Protects people from getting confused: Quality Label protects people from searching for info on the internet and getting incorrect results.

2.2 Description

The Quality Label is a pictogram inspired by the icons created for the website. In particular we choose to mix the level of the material (Table 1: Icon for LEVEL) and the type of user (Table 2: Icon for TYPE OF USER). The resulting icons and its meaning, with examples of material, are reported in the tables below (Table 3: Icon for QUALITY LABEL)

Table 2: Icon for LEVEL

SUBJECT MATTER	ICON	MEANING
Basic		For people with very low, basic knowledge on the topic
Intermediate		For people with intermediate knowledge of the topic
Advance		For people with upper level of knowledge looking for more detailed information on the topic

Table 3: Icon for TYPE OF USER

TYPE OF USER	ICON	MEANING
Student		Didactic material
Citizens		Informative material
Technicians		Technical material

Table 4: Icon for QUALITY LABEL

QUALITY LABEL	ICON BASIC	ICON INTERMEDIATE	ICON ADVANCED
Student			
Meaning	Didactic material useful for students at elementary schools	Didactic material useful for students at high schools	Didactic material useful for students at first year of university
Example	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interactive games and quizzes Simple explanations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Video-clips as tutorials for realisation of demonstrators, explanation of processes and technologies, etc. Role-play game and quizzes; Training videos Informative factsheets, 60 second science videos, etc 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Young careers testimonials Res job profiles and factsheets and requests Lectures/webinars
Citizens			

Meaning	Informative material useful for people with no knowledge “never heard before”	Informative material useful for people with some knowledge	Material useful for people with no technical knowledge
Example	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good practice tips and suggestions, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not scientific article; • News; • Interview; • Informative factsheets; • Good practice applications examples 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good database; practice • Good applications with practice methodologies explanations
Technicians	<p>Advanced Technicians</p>		
Meaning	Material useful for people with technical knowledge in other fields	Material useful for people with some technical knowledge	Material useful for people with technical knowledge
Example	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Webinars; • Scientific papers; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reports 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical Manuals • Guideline • Legislative and policy material

Several materials could be described with more than one icon; a discussion in the consortium will lead the attribution, and if it's not misleading, more than one icon will be given, with a description of the reason for the double application.

2.3 Rules for the quality label application

In order to use the quality label, the material is first evaluated by the consortium to check the validity of the information contained, its level and the utility.

- If the content is not clear and scientific appropriate or valid, the label can NOT be given;
- if the content is not clear but still scientifically correct, or the appropriate icon is not easy to find, the material can be discussed with the Scientific Advisory Board
- If the content is scientifically correct and clear, a short internal discussion can be performed in order to applicate the appropriate icon;

The approach is depicted in the figure below (Figure 2)

Figure 2: Quality label application rules

2.4 The Scientific Advisory Board (SAB)

The Scientific Advisory Board (SAB), a subgroup of the Advisory Board (AB), was defined in M3. The SAB is in charge of supporting AzzerCO2 and the team members in uploading and checking documents, video, lectures on the Green Portal.

The SAB will support the phase of validation of the modules to guarantee the quality of info broadcast, and explanation or description of the material, if required. The SAB will be available to have an open discussion with users.

3. Green Portal Overview

The site map in Figure 1 depicts the different sections, with their description and the possibility to apply filters to search for the info material uploaded. Below the overview of the portal (Figure 3). The didascalies have not been updated at the time of this deliverable finalisation.

Figure 3: Green Portal initial page

The initial page is the presentation of the sections with a short description and the link to all the other pages. Clicking on the section “green woman” as pointed by the yellow arrow (the yellow triangle in the figure above; the triangle will not be actually inserted in the real portal) the portal will lead to the section, as in the figure below (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Portal, section green woman

The arrow in the picture above points to the filters that can be opened to choose between a list of options, as in the picture below (Figure 5).

Green portal

KNOWLEDGE-HUB GREEN WOMAN GREEN SCHOOLS GOOD PRACTICE DATABASE GREEN E-BOARD

project site contact

Green woman

SKILLBILL is a 3-year EU funded Horizon Europe project that aims at creating pathways to induce target groups to get interested or involved in renewable energy sources (RES) besides their initial level of education and their working position by increasing hard and soft skills of potential users and stakeholders and developing interest in the topic using clear and appropriate approaches.

Use filters and find what are you looking for

Quality Label

- Basic/school
- Basic/citiz
- Basic/Technicians
- Intermediate/school
- Intermediate/citizens
- Intermediate/Technicians
- Advantage/school
- Advantage/citizens
- Advantage/Technicians
- None

RES Category

- Solar Energy (thermal and electrical)
- Biomethane/Biogas; Biomass
- Combustion Systems (Combustion and gasification)
- Renewable Fuel (hydrogen, bio-diesel, bio-ethanol)
- Wind Energy
- Fuel Cells and storage
- Geothermal

Language

- ITA
- ENG
- ESP
- PLN
-

Type of material

- video
- interview
- webinar
- publication
-

Basic School

2022

Title

lorem ipsum dolor sic amet

Intermediate School

2022

Title

lorem ipsum dolor sic amet

Advanced Citizens

2022

Title

lorem ipsum dolor sic amet

Advanced Technicians

2022

Title

lorem ipsum dolor sic amet

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General SKILLBILL e-mail address: info@skillbill-project.eu

Coordinator's contact details

AzzeroCO2

Address: Stree Genova 23, 00184, Rome

Link: www.azzeroco2.it

Figure 5: Green Portal “green women” section, choosing a filter

In the page a filter or a label can be chosen, opening the list available, highlighted by the yellow triangle in the figure below (Figure 6); in this case only the material identified by the filter will be visible.

Figure 6: Green Portal “green women” section with filter on

Once a filter or a label is chosen, only the selected material can be visualised (Figure 6)

All the other sections will follow a similar model (Figure 7); in the knowledge hub an additional filter is present.

Green portal

KNOWLEDGE-HUB GREEN WOMAN GREEN SCHOOLS GOOD PRACTICE DATABASE GREEN E-BOARD

project site contact

Knowledge-hub

SKILLBILL is a 3-year EU funded Horizon Europe project that aims at creating pathways to induce target groups to get interested or involved in renewable energy sources (RES) besides their initial level of education and their working position by increasing hard and soft skills of potential users and stakeholders and developing interest in the topic using clear and appropriate approaches.

Use filters and find what are you looking for

Section Quality Label RES Category Language Type of material

▼ ▼ ▼ ▼ ▼

2022

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info@skillbill-project.eu

Coordinator's contact details
AzzeroCO2
Address: Stree Genova 23, 00184, Rome
Link: www.azzeroco2.it

Figure 7: Green Portal “knowledge hub” section

The project

SKILLBILL's overall objective is to develop a large and strong foundation for the growth and acceleration of renewable energy's deployment, thanks to engaging with stakeholders of the whole chain, diffusing scientific culture and skilling multi-level workers. The basic idea underlying the project is that the knowledge should be diffused at several different levels and qualitatively appropriate both to train the adequate number of workers and to increase RES awareness and to reach a more social and inclusive Europe. The project aims at creating several pathways to induce target groups to get interested or involved in RES besides their initial level of education and their working position. It's important, beside the creation of instruments for the upskilling and reskilling of workers, technician and designers, to have awareness modules for unspecific public in order to fight against lack of information, bad quality material, gender gap and the phenomenon of functional illiteracy: it is widely documented that lifelong suitable learning process is the fundamental driver to support the development, maintenance and update of skills. Thus, SKILLBILL proposes concrete actions to accelerate the deployment of renewable energy at different levels to analyse and involve all the interested parts in open discussion using adequate language; create several different pathways to increase skills after having mapped knowledge gap and without gender prejudice; develop and implement innovative learning method; and evaluate the work performed.

Coordinator: **AZZERO CO2 SRL (AzzeroCO2)**

PARTNER	SHORT NAME	
	AZZERO CO2 SRL	AzzeroCO2
	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC	Q-PLAN
	WHITE RESEARCH SPRL	WR
	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DELLA TUSCIA	UNITUS
	UNIVERSIDAD DE SEVILLA	USE
	METROPOLIA AMMATTIKORKEAKOULU OY	METROPOLIA
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	SINERGIE SOC CONS ARL	SINERGIE
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